

How Artificial Intelligence can Help in the Easy-to-Read Adaptation of Numerical Expressions ANNEX: Survey Additional Information

Survey Design

The questionnaire is divided into two main parts: (1) one section that includes ten single-answer multiple choice questions to capture opinions about which linguistic structures are easier or better understood for expressing fractions and percentages; and (2) another section with nine questions related to participants' demographics, knowledge, background, and experience. In the first section, questions are of two different types. Such types of questions used in the questionnaire were validated by a person with cognitive disabilities in a pilot survey before the questionnaire was launched.

- Questions where the participant has to choose an answer. In this case, participants are asked about their preferences or about the simplest answer. The possible answers to those questions consist of (a) sentences including the most typical ways to express percentages (e.g. *el 20% de la población (20% of the population)* and *el veinte por ciento de la población (twenty percent of the population)*) and (b) one or more sentences that are the result of adapting the aforementioned typical ways with an E2R approach in mind, that is, trying to find a synonym formula which is easier to understand (e.g. *unos pocos (a few)* and *un quinto de la población (a fifth of the population)*).
- Questions where participants have to complete a sentence by selecting one of the possible answers. The set of answers includes the most typical ways to express percentages and one or more synonym formulas.

The collection of sentences with the most common representation of percentages used in the questionnaire was built looking for news with numerical expressions in the form of percentages. Synonym formulas were manually built by considering the set of proposals given by E2R experts to adapt percentages (see Section 3). A linguistic expert validated the collection of synonym formulas.

4.2. Survey Participants

118 people responded the questionnaire (64 male, 49 female, and the rest of participants preferred not to provide gender information). Participants include mainly representatives from three different autonomous communities in Spain¹: Andalucía (46.6%), Comunidad Valenciana (25.4%), Madrid (23.7%), one participant from Galicia, one from Extremadura, one from Castilla León, and another one from Cataluña. Most of the participants (57.6%) have a medium level² of reading comprehension, whereas 31.4% has a high level, and 5.1% a low level². Regarding the age range, half of the participants ranged from 31 to 45 years old, 18.6% from 18 to 30, and 21.2% were from 46 to 60. With respect to their impairments, most of the participants (81.9%) have an intellectual disability. One the most frequent occupation in the set of 118 participants is to be user of occupational centres (48.3%), while 11.9% are E2R validators.

¹ Autonomic Federations from Andalucía, Comunidad Valenciana and Madrid played the crucial role of distributing the main goal of this survey as well as the link to the questionnaire through different organizations of people with cognitive or intellectual disabilities.

² It is worth mentioning that the level of comprehension referred to here is based on a specific question in the questionnaire asking participants about their level of reading comprehension.